

India

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITECNICA
DE SAN LUIS POTOSÍ

Dinámica Social & Estilo Empresarial

Academia de Administración y Gestión

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¿Cuáles son las industrias líderes?

¿Qué aspectos económicos sobresalen?

¿Cuáles son las debilidades estructurales?

¿Cómo se define el estilo empresarial?

¿Cómo se componen clases sociales?

1. Contexto en la República de la India

1.1 Ficha Técnica

2.2. Industrias Líderes

3.3. Retos

Prathiba Patil
Presidente R. India

Manmohan Singh
Primer Ministro R. India

भारत गणराज्य
Bhārat Ganarājya
República de la India

सत्यमेव जयते

Bandera

Escudo

• **Capital:** Nueva Delhi

• **Gobierno:** Democrático . Independencia 15/08/1947

• **Población:** 1.2 B (2º)

• **Moneda:** Rupee (INR)

• **PIB:** \$3.209 trillion (2008) - (6.7% - 2009)

• **Fuerza Laboral:** 523.5 M (2008). agri 60%, ind 12%, ser 28% (2003)

• **Comercio:** 4% proporción mundial (WTO 2010)

• **Exportaciones:** \$22.13 B (2008).

• **Socios comerciales** US 15%, RPCh 8.7%, UAE 8.7%(2007). Source: CIA World Fact Book - 2008

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1. Contexto en la República de la India

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Tasa de malnutrición entre los niños menores de tres años - **46 %** (2007).

Personas que viven por debajo de la línea internacional de pobreza (1.25 USA). 60% en 1981 a **42%** en 2005

En **8 estados** viven 421 millones de pobres, once millones más que en naciones africanas. (2010)

United Nation Development Program (UNDP)
2010

2. Dinámica Social

1.1 Sistema de Castas

2.2 Pirámide Poblacional

3.3 Cultura y Religión

"Sistema hereditario de estratificación social (2,500 años). Grupos: endógamos (*jāti*).¹" Hinduismo enseña que la sociedad fue creada del cuerpo de una divinidad: **Brahmā**.

2. Dinámica Social

2.1 Sistema de Castas

2.2. Demografía

2.3 Cultura y Religión

• Desde 2001 se registró población de más de **10 millones** (en algunas cd. (Mumbai-Delhi-Calcuta))

• Más **70%** población reside en zonas rurales.

• Número dialectos: **1,652.**

• Tasa alfabetización **64,8%** (53.7% mujeres y 75.3% hombres). Kerala 91% es el más alto índice.

• Tasa de crecimiento población: 1.38% anual. **22** nacimientos por cada 1,000 personas.

2025

583 MII
↑ 10 veces +
tamaño actual

\$ 378 000 000 000
Monto total de
A.B.T.

291 MII
pobreza extrema a
una vida sostenible

5.3%
↑ ingreso familiar
promedio

5°
Ranking de
mercado de
consumo.

****Clase Media****

13,4%
↑ anual
confección

12 veces
+ consumo de
comunicación

10,5%
↑ mercado de
combustibles

2. Dinámica Social

1.1 Sistema de Castas

2.2 Demografía

3.3 Cultura y Religión

Fieles a sus festivos y su religión

CELEBRATION TIME: Schoolgirls perform the traditional Punjabi folk dance of giddha on the eve of the Basant Panchami in Amritsar on Friday. The festival marks the start of the spring season after the rigours of winter. PHOTO: AP

Regal splendour

DEVOTEE'S DELIGHT: Priest of Sri Lakshmi Ganapati temple on NH 5 near Thatichetlapalem Balu Swamy giving the finishing touches to 'Raja alankaram' of Ganesha idol on the final day of Ganesha Navaratri in Visakhapatnam on Monday. - PHOTO: C. V. SUBRAHMANYAM

En conflicto con la modernidad y sus tradiciones

We don't need no (sex) education

We can no longer afford to dwell in the corridor of uncertainty when it comes to sex and sexuality...

We'll not spare dating couples on Valentine's Day: Muthalik

Bangalore Bureau

BANGALORE: After their recent attack on young women at a Mangalore pub, the Sri Ram Sene has now announced an action plan to target couples found dating on February 14, Valentine's Day.

At a press conference here on Thursday, Sri Ram Sene leader Pramod Muthalik, who is now on bail, said Sene activists across Karnataka would not only hold protests outside

colleges, hostels and hotels, where Valentine's Day celebrations are held, but also forcibly marry off couples found dating in public.

"Our activists will go around with a priest, a turmeric stub and a 'māngal sūtra' on February 14. If we come across couples being together in public and expressing their love, we will take them to the nearest temple and conduct their marriage," he said. If the couples resisted

the move, the girl would be forced to tie a 'rakhi' to the boy.

Mr. Muthalik said his outfit would ensure that Valentine's Day greeting cards were not sold. Activists would check out stores that sold such cards.

Asked if his men would use physical force against those celebrating Valentine's Day, Mr. Muthalik said they "will not take the law into their own hands."

Her struggle for justice against honour killing

Sushma's brother murdered her husband, three others to avenge their marriage

Divya Gandhi

BANGALORE: As the Women's Reservation Bill rings in the centennial year of Women's Day on a celebratory note, 25-year-old Sushma Tiwari's story tells of an inspirational fight-back against a brutal form of patriarchy and caste oppression.

It has been a six-year legal battle for Sushma against the horrific 'honour killing' by her brother of almost her entire marital family: husband Prabhu Nochil, her father-in-law and two minors in their home near Mumbai, all to avenge her marriage into a family of a 'lower' caste. Sushma is from a Brahmin family of UP, and Prabhu, an Ezhava from Kerala.

Although the fast track sessions court in Maharashtra, and later the Bombay High Court, awarded the death penalty to Sushma's brother Dilip Tiwari and his accomplices, the Supreme Court in December 2009 reduced the sentence to 25-year imprisonment.

This February, Sushma filed a review petition questioning the decision to let the perpetrators of this crime.

In 2004, seven months after the couple got married, Dilip and his associates

Sushma Tiwari in Bangalore on Thursday. — PHOTO: BHAGYA PRAKASH K.

four members of the family, and grievously injured others. A pregnant woman, a relative. The court, exercising its decision to revoke the sentence, said: "It is

a common experience that when the young sister commits something unusual and as an inter-caste community marriage, secret love affair, then in society it is the eldest brother who

or otherwise is held responsible for not stopping such [an] affair."

It added: "If he became the victim of his wrong genuine caste conflict it would

the caste, community, religion, though totally unjustified, is a stark reality."

"Totally illegal"

Sushma has challenged this reasoning, stating this perception "is wrong and totally illegal under our Constitution and various laws of the land like the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989" and "can never be made a ground for lessening a sentence. In fact, these feelings of caste hatred are themselves criminal..."

Her petition states: "In fact, mass killings based on the concept of 'honour' must be viewed by this Hon'ble Court as murders which must be given the highest deterrent sentence."

In Bangalore recently to attend the National Young Women's convention organised by the All India Democratic Women's Association (AIDWA), this resolute young woman told *The Hindu* that by reducing the sentence, the highest court of the land has sent out a wrong message to all those who are out of caste in the sake of hu-

Diversidad religiosa

VENTING THEIR IRE: Indian students and supporters stage a rally in Melbourne on Sunday condemning the recent attacks on the Indian student community and demanding justice for the victims of the assaults. The "peace rally," which kicked off from outside the Royal Melbourne Hospital, saw chanting of slogans such as "Bharat Mata Ki Jai."

3. Estilo Empresarial

3.1 Los 10 aspectos básicos para una negociación exitosa

1

Negocios familiares, no confían el negocio a personas ajenas

2

Don de gentes es valorado más que su experiencia

3

Suelen ser "esquivos" en sus respuestas.

4

No aceptan haber problemas aun que la realidad sea lo contrario.

5

Entre ellos solo se tratan con personas del mismo nivel

6 Negociaciones suelen ser bastante pausadas y tranquilas

7 La hospitalidad es una parte básica para agradar a sus visitantes.

8 Al primer ofrecimiento de cualquier tipo lo mejor es tratar de rechazarlo.

9 Las tardanzas y los retrasos suelen ser habituales

10 Las mujeres locales no suelen ocupar ningún tipo de puesto

4. Nuestro Compromiso

4.1 ¿Cuál fue el mayor aprendizaje?

PIB (nominal) Puesto
14° Total (2009)
US\$ 874.902
millones

México es el
mayor productor
de plata en el mundo.

11° lugar a nivel
mundial número de
habitantes

Cd México
segunda +
poblada del mundo

El golfo +
grande del
mundo (1.500.000
km²)

700 especies de
cactus, 518 son de
origen mexicano.

Cd México más
antigua del Continente
(1325)

Cd México mayor
número de museos en
mundo

Primera
imprenta y
biblioteca (siglo
XVI).

Castillo
Chapultepec es el
único castillo en
Continente

Primera
patente tv colores
(1940) Camarena
(23 años)

iSe lo debemos a
nuestro país!

India

Dinámica Social & Estilo Empresarial

Gracias por su atención!